

EVALUATION OF THE EMBEDDED SPAR

COMPOSITE DESIGN CONCEPT*

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Experimental data indicates that the incorporation of an insert into an integral composite joint (embedded spar concept) increases the out-of-plane load transfer capability {1,2}. The detailed design of the embedded spar concept has been conducted with linear-elastic finite element techniques for the graphite-epoxy material system. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion has been employed to predict joint strength and correlation with experimental results shows relatively close agreement.

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Introduction

Multidirectional laminates made up of discrete layers of unidirectional lamina of prescribed fiber orientations enables the designer to optimize the structural configuration with respect to inplane force resultants only. The absence of fibers oriented normal to the plane in these layers results in the low interlaminar strength properties typical of the resin phase of the material. Consequently, the out-of-plane loading of laminates is severely limited by the interlaminar strength of advanced composite materials. Development of optimum out-of-plane load transfer mechanisms is required. The detailed design of the embedded spar concept referenced in this paper will enable the designer to optimize the joint configuration with respect to out-of-plane force resultants {2}.

Geometry and Loading Conditions

The geometry and loading conditions for the integral joint investigated in this report are based upon the results presented in the WICAD Program by General Dynamics Corporation {1}. The embedded spar concept consists of an integral lower cover and spar where an insert is co-cured simultaneously with these components to improve joint strength. Details of the integrally bonded substructure are shown schematically in Figure 1 where the multi-spar design is evident. The critical load for the integral joint is the skin pull-off load caused by a maximum internal fuel pressure (P) of 45 psi. Beam theory was employed to reduce the multi-spar construction to a single integral joint with appropriate boundary conditions. The Structural Analysis Program (SAPIV) was then employed in the linear-elastic finite element analysis of the embedded spar concept.

Figure 1. Embedded Spar Concept

The length of wingskin was chosen to be 3.38 inches which corresponds to the zero moment boundary conditions at the ends of the wingskin and a shear resultant of magnitude 2.3P lb./in. The zero moment boundary condition was enforced by placing no restriction on the displacement of finite element nodes situated at the end of the wingskin. The shear resultant was approximated by a discontinuous parabolic distribution consisting of concentrated nodal forces. The critical fuel pressure loading for the wingbox design was modeled as a uniform pressure loading, P applied to the top surface of the wingskin only. The X, Y, and Z translations and rotations for the nodes at the top of spar were fixed so that the reaction to the applied loading is obtained. To ensure symmetry about the centerline, the Y translation of nodes along the centerline was also fixed. The loading and boundary conditions for a typical finite element model of the embedded spar with a titanium insert are shown clearly in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Typical Finite Element Simulation of the Embedded Spar

Parametric Results

The geometric parameters investigated included the insert flange thickness, flange length, web length, spar overlap thickness; and the length of spar overlap. Both titanium and unidirectional graphite-epoxy insert concepts were studied. In addition, two wingskin laminate configurations were also considered.

Parametric results are presented as design curves to be employed in assessment of embedded spar strength. The reader may utilize any desired failure criterion and material strength properties to predict joint strength since all stress components, interlaminar normal stress (σ_z), interlaminar shear stress (σ_{23}), and the inplane stress (σ_x) are presented at locations throughout the structure as a function of the geometric parameters mentioned above. Finite element results for the titanium insert concept having wingskin laminate configuration $\{(0/+45/0)_4 (+45)_2 (0/+45/0)_2\}_s$, indicates that the insert flange thickness and flange length are the critical geometric parameters affecting strength. Identification of four failure mechanisms were made as follows: bending and interlaminar normal stress failure modes at the base of the spar; bending stress failures in the overlap and wingskin at the end of the flange. Incorporation of 90° plies into the wingskin laminate near the wingskin surface ($\{(+45/90)_2(0/+45/0)_6\}_s$) eliminates the bending failure mode in the wingskin.

The wingskin laminate configuration (56 plies) is modeled as six sub-laminates in the finite element model. The sublaminates employed for finite element modeling of wingskin laminate configurations, 1 and 2, are given below:

	Wingskin 1	Wingskin 2
Row 1	$(0/+45/0)_4$	$(+45/90)_2(0/+45/0)_3$
Row 2	$(+45)_2(0/+45/0)_2$	$(0/+45/0)_3$
Row 3	$(+45)_2(0/+45/0)_2$	$(0/+45/0)_3$
Row 4	$(0/+45/0)_2$	$(0/+45/0)_2$
Row 5	$(0/+45/0)$	$(0/+45/0)$
Row 6	$(0/+45/0)$	$(+45/90)_2$

The spar consists of 24 plies of $+45^\circ$ graphite-epoxy composite material, which separates into the 12 ply overlap at the base of the spar. The desired overlap geometry onto the wingskin is obtained by reduction of the number of plies in the overlap at desired locations. Only the most pronounced variations in the stress distribution as a function of the geometric parameters mentioned above will be discussed for the titanium insert concept. This will, however, clearly demonstrate the scope of the detailed design of the embedded spar concept found in reference 2.

Influence of Flange Thickness on Stress Distribution

The major advantage of incorporating an insert into the joint is presented in Figures 3 and 4, where dramatic reductions in the interlaminar and bending stress components at the base of the spar are observed. In terms of component strength, the addition of a titanium insert with a flange thickness of 0.088 inches increases the spar strength from approximately 2.0 to 3.0 for failures occurring at the base of the spar. The interlaminar and bending stress components are both primarily the result of the bending deformation of the wingskin under the uniform pressure loading. An increase in flange thickness is equivalent to an increase in flexural stiffness which reduces the curvature at the base of the spar and consequently the interlaminar and bending stress components.

The influence of flange thickness t on the stress components at the end of the flange is complex and is a strong function of the overlap thickness. A large bending stress component exists for all overlap geometries due to the sudden reduction in stiffness and the corresponding increase in curvature at the end of the flange. In addition, one observes that as overlap thickness increases, the bending stress in the overlap as a function of increasing t , changes from a slightly decreasing to a rapidly increasing function. The interlaminar stress components at this site are directly proportional to flange thickness and inversely proportional to overlap thickness (see Figures 5 and 6). This phenomena is attributable to a change in the load transfer mechanism at the end of the flange.

Investigation of the asymptotic behavior of the stress components at the end of the flange as $t \rightarrow 0$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$ will explain the observed phenomena. As $t \rightarrow 0$, the stress distribution at the end of the flange should approach a state of pure bending where the interlaminar stress component is equal to the applied pressure on the surface and decays within the wingskin. Note that the data points for $t = 0$ in Figures 5 and 6 do not agree with the above statement because these points correspond to both zero flange thickness and zero flange length. As $t \rightarrow \infty$, the fibers rotate 90° from the x - y plane to the x - z plane at the end of the flange. In this configuration, the interlaminar normal and shear stress components will become maximum and the inplane stress will diminish.

In summary, the above discussion indicates that the inplane bending stress will pass through a maximum value and the interlaminar stress components will increase as the ratio of flange to overlap thickness increases. Inspection of Figures 5 and 6 does indeed show the interlaminar stress components are directly proportional to the ratio of flange to overlap thickness. In addition, the bending stress components are found to pass through a maximum at a ratio of flange to overlap thickness of approximately one.

Figure 3. Maximum Bending Stress Components at Base of Spar as a Function of Insert Flange Thickness

Figure 4. Maximum Interlaminar Normal Stress Component at Base of Spar as a Function of Insert Flange Thickness

Figure 5. Maximum Bending Stress Component at End of Flange as a Function of Insert Flange Thickness: 4 Ply Overlap

Figure 6. Maximum Bending Stress Component at End of Flange as a Function of Insert Flange Thickness: 12 Ply Overlap

Influence of Flange Length on Stress Distribution

An understanding of the behavior of stress components at the end of the flange as a function of flange length can be obtained from simple beam theory. The moment distribution, initially zero at the ends of the wingskin increases as one approaches the spar. Therefore, an increase in flange length extends the ends of the flange into an area of lower moment. In the limit as the flange length approaches the length of the wingskin, the moment approaches a minimum which forces the bending stress at this location to do the same. The magnitude of the bending stress component at the end of the flange is proportional to the discontinuity in flexural stiffness. A finite moment coupled with an order of magnitude variation in flexural stiffness across the discontinuity produces the singular nature of the bending stress distribution at the end of the flange. Examination of the bending stress at the end of the flange (Figures 7) clearly demonstrates the deleterious effect of incorporating a flange of small aspect ratio (length to thickness) into the structure. The bending stress passes through a maximum before diminishing with increase in flange length as discussed above.

Influence of Length of Overlap on Stress Distribution

The major effect of the length of overlap on the stress distribution occurs at the end of the overlap as shown in Figure 8. An increase in overlap length reduces all stress components at this location. The reduction of the bending stress with an increase in overlap length results in an increase in spar strength and a potential transition from a bending failure at the end of the overlap to another of the remaining failure modes discussed previously. This trend is expected since an increase in overlap length translates the end of the overlap to a region of lower moment. The interlaminar stress components are generated primarily by the load-transfer from the insert and overlap to the wingskin. An increase in overlap length, essentially allows transfer of an equivalent total load over a larger area and consequently produces a reduction in interlaminar stress component at the end of the overlap.

Figure 7. Maximum Bending Stress Component at End of Flange as a Function of Insert Flange Length

Figure 8. Maximum Bending Stress Component at End of Overlap as a Function of Overlap Length

Figure 9. Maximum Interlaminar Normal Stress Component on Top Surface of Flange as a Function of Insert Web Length

Influence of Titanium Web Length on Stress Distribution

An interesting phenomena is observed at the base of the spar as the web length is varied. Load transfer from the composite web to the insert is accomplished through two primary mechanisms. The first is the load transfer by shear stress acting on the composite-titanium web interface and the second mode is by interlaminar normal stress acting on the top surface of the flange. Therefore, a reduction of one mechanism stress must result in an increase of the second mechanism stress since the total load transfer must remain constant. A reduction in web length reduces the amount of load transferred by shear stress and one would expect a corresponding increase in interlaminar normal stress. In Figure 9 an increase in interlaminar normal stress as the web length is reduced is observed. Analogously, an increase in interlaminar shear stress at the composite-titanium web interface occurs when the web length is increased as shown in Figure 10. However, the variation of stress components with titanium web length does not appreciably alter the predicted embedded spar strength.

Correlation of Finite-Element and Experimental Results

The test specimen geometries for the no-insert and titanium insert concepts are shown in Figures 11 and 12, respectively. The test procedure consisted of applying a tensile load through the spar and reacting the load through simple supports at the ends of the wingskin with a span of 3.6 inches. The prediction of the experimental load-deflection response requires that a finite element analysis of the exact test specimen geometry and loading conditions be executed. In Figure 13, the correlation between experimental and the finite element load-deflection response for the no-insert concept is found to be very good. The experimental data is observed to be reproducible and exhibit linear-elastic behavior in agreement with the finite element predictions. Consequently, confidence is generated in the finite element model as an accurate description of the embedded spar integral joint. More importantly, however, the close agreement indicates that the inplane and

Figure 10. Interlaminar Shear Stress Component at Base of Spar on Composite-Web Interface as a Function of Insert Web Length

Figure 11. No-Insert Test Specimen Geometry

interlaminar material properties employed to describe the overall response of the spar material and the wingskin as six sublaminates represents a good representation of the actual element.

Correlation of finite element prediction and the experimental load-deflection response for the titanium insert concept is shown in Figure 14. A bi-linear response is observed experimentally, and assuming the initial elastic region is generated by inherent insert deformation, comparison of the secondary stiffness with the finite element prediction indicates relatively good agreement.

The Tsai-Wu failure criterion may be expressed in tensor notation for the lamina coordinate system as follows:

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad (i, j = 1-6) \quad (1)$$

where failure occurs when the magnitude of the expression exceeds unity. The F_i and F_{ij} are failure tensors defined as functions of the material strength properties,

$$F_i = \frac{1}{X_i^T} - \frac{1}{X_i^C} \quad (i = 1-3) \quad F_i = \frac{1}{S_i^+} - \frac{1}{S_i^-} \quad (i = 4-6) \quad (2)$$

$$F_{ii} = \frac{1}{X_i^T X_i^C} \quad (i = 1-3) \quad F_{ii} = \frac{1}{S_i^+ S_i^-} \quad (i = 4-6) \quad (3)$$

Figure 12. Titanium Insert Test Specimen Geometry

Figure 13. Comparison of Finite Element and Experimental Load-Deflection Response of the No-Insert Concept

and the interaction term F_{ij} must satisfy the following stability criterion:

$$F_{ij} \leq \sqrt{F_{ii}F_{jj}} \quad (i, j = 1-6). \quad (4)$$

The multiaxial failure criterion prediction of the embedded spar strength where σ_1 , σ_5 , and σ_6 are zero and F_4 , F_5 , and F_6 terms vanish reduces to the following:

$$F_2\sigma_2^2 + F_3\sigma_3^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{33}\sigma_3^2 + F_{44}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2F_{23}\sigma_2\sigma_3 + 2F_{34}\sigma_3\sigma_{23} + 2F_{24}\sigma_2\sigma_{23} = 1 \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_4 = \sigma_{23}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} F_2 &= \frac{1}{X_2^T} - \frac{1}{X_2^C} & F_{22} &= \frac{1}{X_2^T X_2^C} & F_{23} &= \sqrt{F_{22}F_{33}} \\ F_3 &= \frac{1}{X_3^T} - \frac{1}{X_3^C} & F_{33} &= \frac{1}{X_3^T X_3^C} & F_{34} &= \sqrt{F_{33}F_{44}} \\ F_4 &= \frac{1}{S_4^+} - \frac{1}{S_4^-} = 0 & F_{44} &= \frac{1}{S_4^2} & F_{24} &= \sqrt{F_{22}F_{44}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Figure 14. Comparison of Finite Element and Experimental Load-Deflection Response of the Titanium Insert Concept

Table I
Strength Allowables

	X_2^T (Ksi)	X_2^C (Ksi)	X_3^T (Ksi)	X_3^C (Ksi)	S_4 (Ksi)
{±45} graphite-epoxy laminates (fibers in X-Y plane)	22	22	10	30	12
±45 graphite-epoxy laminates (fibers in X-Z plane)	22	22	10	30	12
{0/±45/0} graphite-epoxy laminates	20	38	10	30	12
{±45/90 ₂ } graphite-epoxy laminates	102	102	10	30	12

Figure 15. Comparison of Finite Element and Experimental Failure Load as a Function of Flange Thickness for the Titanium Insert Concept

The effective material strength properties for the various sublaminates considered are found in Table I. The following expression for the factor of safety is derived from the Tsai-Wu criterion:

$$N = \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad (7)$$

where N = factor of safety $\left(\frac{\text{Failure load}}{\text{Design load}}\right)$

$$a = (F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{33}\sigma_3^2 + F_{44}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2F_{23}\sigma_2\sigma_3 + 2F_{34}\sigma_3\sigma_{23} + 2F_{24}\sigma_2\sigma_{23}) \quad (8)$$

$$b = (F_2\sigma_2 + F_3\sigma_3) \quad (9)$$

$$c = -1 \quad (10)$$

The Tsai-Wu failure criterion was next employed in conjunction with the design curves to predict failure strength as a function of titanium flange thickness. The interlaminar normal strength ($X_3^T=10$ Ksi) is chosen to force agreement for the no-insert concept. Figure 15³ shows excellent correlation of predicted and experimental strengths (design load = 360 lb./in.).

Conclusions

Linear-elastic finite element analysis has been employed to identify methods for increasing the out-of-plane strength of an integral spar-wingskin joint (embedded spar). Analytical results consist of design curves where the interlaminar normal stress, interlaminar shear stress, and the inplane bending stress components are presented as a function of various geometric parameters. This enables the reader to employ any desired failure criterion and material strength properties for prediction of embedded spar strength. Correlation of experimental and finite element results show excellent agreement and indicate that the design data presented represent an accurate description of the integral joint behavior.

Nomenclature

a,b,c	Coefficients
F_i, F_{ii} (i=1,6)	Tsai-Wu strength tensor element
F_{ij} (i,j=1,6)	Tsai-Wu strength tensor element
N	Factor of safety $\left(\frac{\text{Failure loads}}{\text{Design load (360 lb./in.)}}\right)$
P	Pressure loading (45 psi)
S_i (i=4,6)	Ultimate shear strength of laminate
t	Flange thickness
X_i^C (i=1,3)	Ultimate compressive strength of laminate
X_i^T (i=1,3)	Ultimate tensile strength of laminate
σ_2	Finite element stress component inplane of fibers
σ_3	Interlaminar finite element normal stress component
σ_{23}	Interlaminar finite element shear stress component

References

1. Maske, E. B., et. al., "Wing/Inlet Composite Advanced Development," AFFDL-TR-70-88, Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB, (1976).
2. Pipes, R. B. and Gillespie, J. W., "Evaluation of the Embedded Spar Composite Design Concept," AFFDL-TR-77-137, Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB, (1978).

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